

DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNICAL COMPETENCE IN PREPARING STUDENTS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *In modern conditions, the modernization of the educational system is carried out, the basis of which is the competence paradigm. Within the framework of this paradigm, the educational process is aimed at the formation of educational results expressed in competencies in students, the formation of which indicates the readiness of the learners to perform certain professional activities*

Keywords: *competence, competence, professional competence, research competence, component, independent learning, knowledge, skill, qualification, personal qualities.*

Every modern specialist in the field of general and special pedagogical research, as a rule, has "reconciled" with existing competencies. Learning is a process of transformation, sustainable development, taking into account the needs and learning needs of Belgian students. The main purpose of vocational training is to determine the level and qualifications of a trained employee, competitiveness in the labor market, competence, responsibility, vocational education, professional activity, a world of standards where labor efficiency is stable, constant and sustainable a professionally trained student, a social and professional mobile person for as long as necessary.

An analysis of the modern state of the process of professional training of students studying in educational institutions shows that the results of this training are reflected, first of all, in various competencies, which consist of a set of knowledge that is mastered by students, and its constitutes an integrative description, indicates the ability to carry out future professional activities.

Approaches to reflexive analysis of the essence of the concept of professional competence provide for the consequential implementation of abilities in a particular field of professional activity, the manifestation of their skills and knowledge and experience, the fulfillment of professional obligations by the subject. It is complemented by the essence of professional competence by determining its types. The generalization of the materials of the study makes it possible to distinguish the following approaches:

a) is a cognitive, effective and volitional competence that is mutually interchangeable, independent and mutually interchangeable, and is formed and developed within a framework that is interesting to the subject.

b) design, information, prediction, organizational, communicative and analytical competencies, in which the criterion is specific skills in a specialist "formation", from the design of the process of professional activity it is considered to be staggering up to the assessment.

c) Professional-pedagogical, communicative, socio-psychological and scientific competencies.

g) special, social, individual and personal competence, criterion-in a specific professional area of the subject, communication, self-development maturity.

Theoretical analysis of approaches to the components of competencies in the field of professional activity made it possible to conclude that it may contain the following components:

- informational-content, process and personal;
- knowledge, skills and skills in the field of professional communication, self-development, self-assessment, professional growth, developed social reflection abilities;
- intellectual-personal resource basis and principle-based part;
- motivational, process and reflexive blocks, respectively personal and value-reflects meaningful, technological and evaluation-meaningful aspects;
- basic, personal, mental-providing, social-providing and professional components that represent technological content in normative, personal-conditioned and professional competence.

The design of economic processes of students is a specially organized educational process for the creation of a project with a specially organized economic effect, which includes the subjective and objective novelty of the problem. This process, together with the integration of theoretical, motivational, practical readiness for effective project economic activities, increases the experience of personal work on the development of projects and determining their economic efficiency.

Scientific research on readiness to carry out activities according to their analysis, the design of economic processes of students makes it possible to define as integrative personal education, which conditions their readiness for activity. Design of economic processes of students preparation for activity-integrative education in the personality component, integrating the values of professional activity of specialists in the direction of economics, the content of knowledge and skills on personality, the discovery of ideas for changing reality, their implementation in projects and project solutions, understanding the specific role of project activities in organizing the solution of economic issues arising in the profession, is reflected in an adequate assessment of the effectiveness and social orientation of the implementation of an economic project. In the structural sense, such preparation includes the following cognitive, motivational-valued, conative, and reflexive components.

It is necessary that the specific components of preparing students for economic process design activities are reflected in the following in our eyes:

for the cognitive component – this is management, marketing and social commerce, enterprise management in modern conditions, especially in the context of the innovation economy, uncertainty and risk, knowledge about these areas and taking into account the system of concepts, "economic project" and "project solution" in essence knowledge of concepts, "assets", knowledge of the causes of the conflict of economic interests in;

motivational-for a valuable component-this is an internal deterministic and professionally motivated, positive professional relationship with knowledge, understanding the role of the project and a special form of project activity, organizing the solution of problems that may arise, the presence of motivation and ability to work in uncertainty and risk conditions, being able to apply special knowledge on the design of economic solutions in;

for the reflexive component – it is generally professional economic is a developed reflexive culture in activity. The ability to determine the goals of controlling the level of knowledge and economic solutions and predict their results, strive for professional skills, self –development in economics and management, evaluate its professional activities, improvisation and foresight, reflexion of its effectiveness in socially oriented project-economic activities.

In order to form the creative abilities of students in the educational process, they must be you should always be encouraged to ask questions. It is necessary to show how the question arises

from nowhere, to clarify the contradictions at the end of the lesson. In the current period, it is not so important to give students a certain set of information and recommendations, their independent acquisition of information and its transformation into knowledge for it is important that it has clear approaches. In this problematic Educational Technology hand comes

The main goal of problem education technology is to increase the independence and activity of learners, to improve their thinking development consists in strengthening the practical application of acquired knowledge. The main feature of the technogony of problem education is the increase in the mental activity of the learner, independent creative search, new knowledge for oneself,

it consists of discovering skills and competencies.

The main psychologic pedagogical goals of problem training are as follows:

- develop the student's thinking circle and abilities, develop their creative skills development;
- the acquisition by students of knowledge and skills acquired during the period of independent solution and active research of the problem, this results in these knowledge and skills much more than in traditional teaching will be solid;
- non-standard problem-seeker, active of the learner and the learner nurture creative personality;
- development of professional problem thinking – has its own characteristics in each specific activity.

Thus, the problem is not put directly, without any preparation. U

it is stated as the main issue in the entire lesson. The complexity of the problems posed should naturally correspond to the level of students. The material to be introduced should not be too large. Materials, in particular, only if the issues can be solved by the students themselves, their potential for solving problems increases. In order to organize the lesson in a problematic way, at the first time, the student must be prepared to argue, freely express his thoughts, react critically. For this, concepts that depend on the problems posed are brought to the surface. Then the problem is clarified and certain conclusions are drawn. This process is expressed in feedback.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth saying that in modern conditions, the use of problematic educational technology in educational practice develops the ability to independently, critically and creatively think in students, while ensuring an effective course of the teaching process. The social requirements imposed on improving the quality and effectiveness of education require teachers to purposefully, effectively apply project and problematic educational technologies in the teaching process. So problematic education thinking in students, decision making ability to make, substantiate one's own opinion formation helps to effectively form Skills, Qualifications. Zero, based on thinking, analysis of knowledge mastering ensures that they are solid, thorough. In addition, the activities of students in the educational process increase their training focus analysis of educational material, listening with such as making, comparing, drawing conclusions development of mental activities helps.

In summary, the analysis of the sources allowed us to draw the following conclusions.

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